

The coherency of motion of two stereocilia depends on the viscoelastic properties of their link

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Abstract. Inner hair-cell hair bundles (IHBs) are the sensory organelles required for hearing. An IHB comprises tens of stereocilia, arranged in 3 to 5 rows of differing heights. Neighboring stereocilia are coupled by extracellular links and fluid. IHBs convert sound induced forces within the hearing organ into receptor currents, which induce the transmission of sound signals to the brain. This process, called mechano-electrical transduction, involves ion channels that open and close in response to IHB deflections caused by sound-induced forces. We show for a model of a hair bundle with two stereocilia how the power spectrum and the coherency of stereocilium displacements depend on the stiffness and damping of the stereocilia and their links. The power spectrum quantifies the noise-driven motion of stereocilia at each frequency, whereas the coherency quantifies the relative motion between stereocilia. We find that the coherency is zero at frequencies corresponding to a transition between vibration modes.

INTRODUCTION

Inner-hair-cell hair bundles are responsible for the transduction of sound induced forces into receptor currents, which results into an electrical signal that can be interpreted by the brain (Fig. 1). The displacement and the receptor current of inner-hair-cell hair bundles depend on their stereocilium heights, widths and the pivot positions, on the mechanical properties (stiffness and damping) of their stereocilia, gating springs and connectors, and on the fluid coupling neighboring stereocilia. We aim to determine the stiffness and damping of the stereocilia and the links and the fluid-coupling damping by measuring the displacement of stereocilium tops owing to inherent noise forces. The power spectra corresponding to these displacements quantifies their motions over a broad range of noise frequencies. By comparing the power spectra obtained experimentally to those derived from a mathematical model of the hair bundle, it is possible to calculate its mechanical properties [1, 2]. In this paper, we show for a simple model of two connected stereocilia how their power spectra depend on the stiffness and damping of their anchors and links.

FIGURE 1. The inner-hair-cell hair bundle comprises stereocilia, attached to the hair-cell apex by rootlets. The stereocilia are arranged in rows of increasing height, linked by gating springs. One column of a hair bundle is shown, comprising three rows of stereocilia. When the stereocilia are stimulated, they pivot, stretching the gating springs and opening ion-channels, through which the receptor current flows. The receptor current depolarizes the cell, inducing the transmission of a sound signal to the brain.

POWER SPECTRUM AND COHERENCY DEPEND ON ANCHOR AND LINK STIFFNESS AND DAMPING

An inner-hair-cell bundle has many stereocilia in each row. Stereocilia in the same row are of similar height and are connected by links. The power spectrum and the coherency of the stereocilia motion depend on the stiffness and damping of their attachment to the hair-cell apex (anchors) and on the stiffness and damping of their links. We study the simple case of a model of a hair bundle with only two connected stereocilia in the first row (Fig. 2). Because they are part of the same row, we assume that they have the identical anchor stiffness k_A and damping λ_A . Their link is represented by a viscoelastic element with a stiffness k_L and damping λ_L [3].

FIGURE 2. Schematic for the model of a hair bundle with two connected stereocilia. The attachment of each stereocilium is represented by an anchor stiffness k_A and an anchor damping λ_A , while their link is characterized by a link stiffness k_L and a link damping λ_L . y is the displacement in the direction of increasing stereocilium height.

The power spectrum of the individual stereocilia and their coherency change as a function of the stiffness and damping. We use values of the stiffness and damping of IHBs measured using non-contact acoustic frequency modulation atomic force microscopy (P13-P14 mice, 5 kHz characteristic frequency) [4]: $k_{HB} = 2.34 \text{ mN.m}^{-1}$ and $\lambda_{HB} = 10.5 \text{ nN.s.m}^{-1}$. If we divide these values by the number of stereocilia in the first row [5], $N = 16$, we get estimates for the anchor stiffness and damping of an individual stereocilium: $k_A = 146 \text{ }\mu\text{N.m}^{-1}$ and $\lambda_A = 0.66 \text{ nN.s.m}^{-1}$. The link stiffness and damping are determined using parameter ratios obtained from measurements in rats [3]: $k_L/k_A = 3.85$ and $\lambda_L/\lambda_A = 5.55$. Default model parameters are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Mechanical parameters for a model of two connected stereocilia in the first row of a inner-hair-cell hair bundle.

Name	Symbol	Value	Reference
Anchor stiffness	k_A	$146 \text{ }\mu\text{N.m}^{-1}$	[4, 5]
Anchor damping	λ_A	0.66 nN.s.m^{-1}	[4, 5]
Link stiffness	k_L	$562 \text{ }\mu\text{N.m}^{-1}$	[3, 4, 5]
Link damping	λ_L	4 nN.s.m^{-1}	[3, 4, 5]
Temperature	T	294 K	—

If the anchor stiffness is increased, the plateau of the power spectrum decreases and the corner frequency increases (Fig. 3A). The coherency decreases at low frequencies because as k_A increases, the stereocilia move more independently (Fig. 3B). At high frequencies, their relative motion is dominated by damping and thus the coherency converges to the same value as the default model.

If the anchor damping is increased, the plateau of the power spectrum increases while the corner frequency decreases (Fig. 3A). In contrast to the default model, the coherency decreases with frequency. In general, coherency is determined by the competition between stiffness and damping forces, which decrease stereocilium motions, and damping-associated noise, which increases stereocilium motions but decreases stereocilium correlations.

If the link stiffness is decreased, the plateau of the power spectrum increases and the shape of the power spectrum changes (Fig. 3C). The coherency decreases at low frequencies because as k_L decreases, the stereocilia move more independently (Fig. 3D). At high frequencies, their relative motion is dominated by damping and thus the coherency converges to the same value as the default model. Furthermore, in contrast to the default model, the coherency is negative at low frequencies and positive at high frequencies (Fig. 3D). This change in sign corresponds to a change in

the cross-correlation mode, which switches from negative to positive with increasing frequency. When the stereocilia are positively correlated, they are moving in the same direction. When they are negatively correlated, they are moving in opposite directions.

If the link damping is increased, the plateau of the power spectrum increases and the shape of the power spectrum changes (Fig. 3C). In comparison to the default model, the coherency decreases at low frequencies and increase at high frequencies.

FIGURE 3. Variation of power spectrum and coherency as a function of the anchor and damping parameters. (A,B) The power spectrum and the coherency are shown for the default parameter values k_A and λ_A (purple), when the anchor stiffness is increased to $2k_A$ (orange), and when the anchor damping is increased to $2\lambda_A$ (green). (C,D) The power spectrum and the coherency are shown for the nominal parameter values k_L and λ_L (purple), when the link stiffness is decreased to $k_L/5$ (red), and when the link damping is increased to $5\lambda_L$ (blue).

CONCLUSIONS

We derived the power spectrum and the coherency of two connected stereocilia and showed how they depend on the stiffness and damping of their anchors and links. We note in particular that the coherency can change sign with increasing noise frequency, which implies a change in the mode of vibration from antiphase to in phase.

The experimental measurements of the IHB stiffness and damping we used here have very large standard deviations: $k_{HB} = (2.34 \pm 2)$ mN/m and $\lambda_{HB} = (10.5 \pm 11)$ nN.s/m [6]. This uncertainty arises in part from the model of the stimulus used to interpret the experimental observations. Like all models, the stimulus model required several simplifying assumptions. Because the model of the stimulus needed to interpret noise-driven motions requires very few assumptions, it is possible to reduce the uncertainties in the estimates of IHB stiffness and damping. In the future, we will use noise-driven motion measurements and a model of the IHB to determine the stiffness and damping of IHB stereocilia and links.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Ondrej Tichacek]: Dear Riccardo, thank you for sharing your study, I found it very informative. I have a few questions and comments:

1. Could you briefly explain the significance of the inter-row connections compared to inter-column connections in the inner-hair-cell hair bundle? How do these connections affect the mechanical properties and functionality of the IHB?
2. If I understand correctly, you estimated the stiffness and damping of the stereocilia in the first row based on measurements from the whole hair bundle (all stereocilia rows). Is this correct? Could you please clarify the assumptions behind this estimation?
3. How do the stiffness and damping properties of stereocilia vary between species, such as rats and mice? Are there significant differences that could influence your results?
4. Could you provide more detail on the method behind your model and simulations? Specifically, how were the data in Figure 3 generated?
5. Can you clarify the noise model used in your study? Is the noise applied to only a single stereocilium, or does it affect multiple elements?
6. I would appreciate a brief introduction to interpreting the power spectrum graphs. For example, what does it mean for the stereocilia motion when you say the plateau of the power spectrum decreases?

[Riccardo Marrocchio]: Hi Ondrej, thank you for questions and comments. Please find my answers below:

1. Stereocilia within the same column are connected by tip-links and connectors. Stereocilia within the same row are connected only by connectors. How different types of links affect the mechanical properties and regulate the function of the IHB is, at present, a matter of speculation. Determining the roles of the connectors is one of our research goals.
2. For our simulations, we used previous experiments to get an estimate of the anchor and link stiffness and damping. From (Cartagena-Rivera et al., *Sci Adv*, 20, 2019) we get the anchor stiffness and the damping of the whole inner-hair-cell hair bundle for P13-P15 mice using non-contact acoustic frequency modulation atomic force microscopy. We divide these numbers by the number of stereocilia in the first row as measured in P11 mice by (Miller et al., *Front Cell Dev Biol*, 25, 2021). The link stiffness and damping are derived from the anchor values using the ratios $\lambda_A/\lambda_L = 0.18$ and $k_A/k_L = 0.26$, as determined in rats (Scharr et al., *J Neurosci*, 22, 2023). These are only rough estimates, which we use in simulations to validate our approach. Our goal is to determine the mechanical properties of the IHB using fewer assumptions and with less error.
3. Non-mammalian stereocilium stiffnesses and damping coefficients seem to be smaller than those in mammalian auditory systems (Scharr et al., *J Neurosci*, 22, 2023). There may be differences between mouse and rat stereocilium stiffnesses and damping coefficients, but the data is inconclusive owing to measurement uncertainties

arising from different developmental ages, cochlear locations, and measurement methods. Our results show that more precise and accurate determinations of stereocilium stiffness and damping are in principle possible.

4. The curves in Figure 3 represent the power spectrum of individual stereocilia and the coherency between two stereocilia as a function of the noise frequency. They were generated from a mathematical model that describes the displacements of two linked stereocilia (schematized in Figure 2, with two viscoelastic elements to represent their attachment to the hair cell apex and their links). From this model we derive the susceptibility matrix of the system and, using the fluctuation dissipation theorem, the power spectra. We will provide a detailed explanation of this model and method in an upcoming paper.
5. Each stereocilium is subjected to noise forces that depend on the mechanical properties of the stereocilia and their links according to the fluctuation-dissipation theorem. In the model, we assume that the noise forces are white and Gaussian.
6. The power spectrum quantifies the variance of an individual stereocilium's displacement as a function of the frequency. If the power spectrum decreases in a certain frequency range (for example in the low-frequency plateau), the displacement variance of the stereocilium in that frequency range decreases. The value of the power spectrum (and the coherency) are determined by competition by noise forces and the constraining forces of stiffness and damping. We will include a more detailed explanation in a longer paper.

[Anthony Peng]: A very nice model of how viscous drag and stereocilia link stiffness affects the power spectrum of stereocilia thermal noise. I personally like the visco-elastic modeling of the mechanical system here. It was surprising to me that in Figure 3C and D that the coherency goes down when the link stiffness is increased (purple to blue). Similarly, I would have thought that increasing link stiffness would lower the power spectral density at low frequencies, since it would have an effect of coupling the stereocilia together more to act as 1 unit, therefore increasing its effective stiffness.

[Riccardo Marrocchio]: Hi Anthony, thank you for your comments. The power spectrum and the coherency are determined by the competition between noise forces and the constraining forces of stiffness and damping. In Figure 3C and D the link stiffness is increased from red to purple. When the link stiffness is increased, the constraining stiffness force increases, decreasing the displacement of the stereocilia and thus reducing their power spectra at low frequencies (Fig. 3C). At high frequencies, the power spectrum mainly depends on the damping and thus the red and purple curves are similar. Increasing the link stiffness causes the coherency to change sign at low frequencies. At low frequencies, the stereocilia move in antiphase (negative coherency) for a small link stiffness and move more in phase (positive coherency) for a large link stiffness. At high frequencies, the stereocilia move in phase for large and small link stiffnesses. Increasing the link stiffness at high frequencies, increases positive correlations between the stereocilia.